

Synthesis of New 2 : 6 Bis Substituted Glycyl and Phenoxy Acetyl Benzo[1,2-d ; 4, 5-d] Bisoxazole

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The parent benzo [1, 2 d , 4, 5-d] bisoxazole 1 react with chloroacetyl chloride giving 2 : 6 bischloroacetyl benzdioxazole 2 which interacts readily with amines and hydrazine. The bis hydrazinoacetyl benzdioxazole 4 on condensation with aldehydes give new schiff bases 5. 1 also reacted with phthalyl amino acid chloride, or with phenoxy acetyl chloride giving the corresponding bisphthalimido acyl benzdioxazole 6, and bis phenoxy acetyl benzdioxazole 8 respectively.

BENZOXAZOLE and other condensed oxazoles find wide application in different industrial and biological aspects^{1, 2, 3}

In the present investigation and in continuity with previous work^{4, 5} attempts were made to

2 Reacted readily⁷ with secondary amines, morphine, piperidine, ephedrine, phenothiazine and anisidine in toluene giving the corresponding 2 : 6 bis glycyl benzdioxazole 3_{a-e}.

The structures of 3 have been established by

prepare different 2 : 6 benzdioxazole derivatives from the parent benzo [1, 2-d , 4, 5-d] bisoxazole⁸ 1. Thus when 1 reacted with chloroacetyl chloride

their analytical data and their IR spectra (C=O, 1700-1685 cm⁻¹)¹⁰

Condensation of one mole of 2 with two moles

in dry toluene gave 2 : 6 bis chloroacetyl benzdioxazole 2 in good yield

of hydrazine hydrate furnished 2 : 6 bis hydrazinoacetyl benzdioxazole 4

The IR spectrum of this compound showed absorption bands at 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O) group and 3380 cm^{-1} (NH) group¹⁰

The structure of compounds 8 was established from the following (i) correct analytical data, (ii) infrared absorption spectra which showed intense

5

5	R
a	C_6H_5
b	$\text{P-CH}_3\text{O-C}_6\text{H}_4-$
c	$\text{O-OH-C}_6\text{H}_4-$
d	$\text{P(CH}_3)_2\text{N-C}_6\text{H}_4-$
e	$\text{P-NO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$
f	$\text{P-OH-C}_6\text{H}_4$

Condensation of 4 with aldehydes in glacial acetic acid furnished the Schiff bases 5

The structures of these compounds were established by their analytical data and IR spectral data which showed absorption bands at 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N), 1695 cm^{-1} (C=O) and 3350 cm^{-1} (NH) stretching frequency¹⁰

absorption bands corresponding to C=O groups¹⁰ at about $1700\text{-}1670\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and phenolic -C-O vibration band near 1280 cm^{-1}

Experimental

Infrared spectra were determined in KBr pellets on Unicam SP 200 G infrared spectrophotometer. All melting points are uncorrected.

6

6, 7	R
a	H
b	CH_3-
c	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}-$
d	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}$

7

8

8	R
a	P-NO_2
b	P-Cl
c	O-NO_2
d	O-Cl

2 Reacted also with phthalyl amino acid chlorides⁹ in dioxane and in presence of triethylamine as a catalyst to give quantitative yield of 2,6-bis-phthalimide acyl-benzdioxazole 6. The phthalyl group of the latter 6 was removed by hydrazinolysis to give bis-glycyl benzdioxazole 7.

Reaction of 2 with phenoxyacetyl chloride⁹ in dioxane and in presence of triethylamine furnished 2,6-bis-phenoxyacetyl benzdioxazole 8.

The parent benzdioxazole⁶ 1, phthalyl amino acid chloride⁸, and phenoxy acetyl chlorides⁹ were prepared by the known methods.

2,6-bis-chloroacetyl benzdioxazole 2

Chloroacetylchloride (0.02 mol) was added slowly to benzdioxazole (0.01 mol) in dry toluene (150 ml) and the reaction mixture refluxed for 3 hrs. Toluene was removed under reduced pressure, the residue was filtered off and then crystallized from alcohol. Yield 83%, m.p. $102\text{-}3^\circ$.

$C_{12}H_6N_2O_4Cl_2$ (313) Calcd C 46.01 H 2.91 N 8.94
 Found C 46.24 H 2.02 N 9.09

2.6 bis glycylyl benzdioxazole derivatives 3 (a-e)

A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and the appropriate base (0.02 mol) in 20 ml of dry toluene was refluxed for 3 hours. The amine hydrochloride was filtered off, the organic layer extracted with 1N HCl (3 x 30 ml), and the acidic extract neutralized with sodium carbonate solution. The precipitated solid was collected, washed with sodium carbonate solution and then crystallized from alcohol-benzene mixture to give 3_{a-e}.

Table 1 represents the physical and analytical data of the compounds 3_{a-e}.

TABLE 1

Comp No	Yield %	m p °C	Formula (Mol Wt)	Found/Calcd		
				%C	%H	%N
a	65	196-7	$C_{20}H_{22}O_6N_4$ (414)	58.21 58.00	5.45 5.31	13.60 13.52
b	70	159-60	$C_{22}H_{26}N_4O_4$ (410)	64.51 64.99	8.41 8.34	13.74 13.61
c	67	170	$C_{22}H_{24}N_4O_6$ (570)	67.55 67.36	6.14 6.00	9.91 9.82
d	69	193-5	$C_{36}H_{22}N_4S_2O_4$ (638)	61.82 61.70	3.55 3.47	8.81 8.78
e	70	201.3	$C_{26}H_{22}N_4O_6$ (486)	64.30 64.19	4.61 4.52	11.60 11.52

2.6 bis hydrazinoacetyl benzdioxazole 4

A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (99-100%, 0.02 mol) in 15 ml of ethanol was refluxed for 3 hrs. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool, diluted with water and crystallized from ethanol-water to give pale-yellow needles of 4 in 70% yield, m p 210-12°.

$C_{12}H_{12}N_6O_4$ (304) Calcd C 47.36 H 3.94 N 27.63
 Found C 47.51 H 3.98 N 27.71

Preparation of Schiff's bases 5_{a-f}

A solution of 4 (1 mol) and the appropriate aldehyde (2 mol) in glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 2-3 hrs.

The reaction mixture was cooled, poured onto crushed ice and the deposited solid was collected, washed several times with cold water and then crystallized from alcohol to give pale-green products of 5_{a-f}.

Table 2 represents the physical and analytical data of 5.

Preparation of bis phthalimido acyl benzdioxazole derivatives 6

To (0.1 mol) of 1 in dioxane (10 ml), (0.2 mol) of N-phthalyl amino acid chloride in dioxane (5 ml) was added followed by (0.2 mol) of triethylamine, and then allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was treated with 2N HCl, and the precipitated solid was filtered, and recrystallized from ethyl acetate.

TABLE 2

Comp No	Yield %	m p °C	Formula (Mol Wt)	Found/Calcd		
				%C	%H	%N
a	70	180-2	$C_{26}H_{20}N_6O_4$ (480)	65.19 65.00	4.30 4.16	17.61 16.50
b	72	219-20	$C_{28}H_{24}N_6O_6$ (540)	62.35 62.22	4.61 4.44	15.70 15.55
c	75	231.3	$C_{26}H_{20}N_6O_6$ (512)	61.02 60.93	3.98 3.90	16.52 16.40
d	72	203.5	$C_{30}H_{20}N_6O_4$ (566)	63.71 63.60	5.33 5.30	19.90 19.78
e	71	228.30	$C_{28}H_{18}N_6O_6$ (570)	54.82 54.70	3.31 3.15	19.80 19.64
f	78	240.2	$C_{26}H_{20}N_6O_6$ (512)	61.05 60.93	4.01 3.90	16.53 16.40

Table 3 represents the physical and analytical data of 6.

TABLE 3

Comp No	Yield %	m p °C	Formula (Mol Wt)	Found/Calcd		
				%C	%H	%N
a	80	156.8	$C_{28}H_{14}N_4O_6$ (534)	63.07 62.92	2.81 2.62	10.68 10.50
b	83	169.71	$C_{30}H_{18}N_4O_6$ (562)	64.18 64.05	3.31 3.20	10.05 9.96
c	80	187.9	$C_{24}H_{26}N_4O_6$ (618)	66.18 66.02	4.31 4.20	9.21 9.06
d	81	206.8	$C_{28}H_{20}N_4O_6$ (646)	66.98 66.87	4.81 4.64	8.78 8.66

Preparation of bis glycylyl benzdioxazole hydrochloride 7

A mixture of 6 (0.5 g) in ethanol (30 ml), and hydrazine hydrate (10 ml) was refluxed for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was evaporated till dryness, the residue was warmed at 50° for 10 minutes with 25 ml of 2N HCl and allowed to stand at room temperature for 1/2 hrs. The precipitated phthalic hydrazide was filtered, the filtrate was evaporated under vacuum to give compounds 7 and recrystallized from ethyl acetate. Table 4 represents the physical and analytical data of 7.

TABLE 4

Comp No	Yield %	m p °C	Formula (Mol Wt)	Found/Calcd		
				%C	%H	%N
a	85	241.3	$C_{18}H_{12}N_4O_4Cl_2$ (347)	41.66 41.50	3.55 3.46	16.21 16.12
b	80	256-9	$C_{14}H_{16}N_4O_4Cl_2$ (375)	44.93 44.80	4.39 4.26	15.13 15.00
c	83	273.5	$C_{16}H_{24}N_4O_4Cl_2$ (431)	50.31 50.11	5.71 5.56	13.16 13.00
d	82	287-9	$C_{20}H_{28}N_4O_4Cl_2$ (459)	52.28 52.28	6.10 6.10	12.20 12.20

Preparation of bis phenoxyacetyl benzdioxazole 8_{a-d}

Substituted phenoxyacetyl chloride (2 mol) in dioxane 10 ml and triethylamine (2 mol) was refluxed with 1 (1 mol) for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered, the filtrate was evaporated under vacuum and the residue was

crystallized from ether and recrystallized from ethyl acetate.

Table 5 represents the physical and analytical data of 8.

TABLE 5

Comp. 8 No.	Yield %	m.p. °C	Formula (Mol. Wt)	Found/Calcd.		
				%C	%H	%N
a	90	209-11	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ (518)	55.48 55.60	2.59 2.70	10.70 10.81
b	91	196-8	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ Cl ₂ (497)	57.81 57.94	2.69 2.81	5.51 5.62
c	89	215-7	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ (518)	55.45 55.60	2.55 2.70	10.69 10.81
d	90	224-6	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ Cl ₂ (497)	57.78 57.94	2.70 2.81	5.50 5.62

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